

Innovations and Trends in Laser Applications for Orthodontics

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Received on: 31 August 2024; Accepted on: 02 September 2024; Published on : 20 October 2024

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Abstract

The area of orthodontics can effectively use a variety of dental lasers that are now in for various applications. Knowledge of parameters of the laser, its power, wavelength is required to produce the good effects on the target area. The benefits of therapy include its potential for painlessness, non-invasiveness, and frequent avoidance of bleeding. The main drawback is the hefty price. When using laser dentistry equipment, it is crucial to take the required precautions to avoid any tissue injury. In this article, we will explore the most common types and features of laser systems used in dentistry, as well as their uses in orthodontics.

Keywords: Lasers, dentistry, orthodontics, painless procedure, target tissue.

Introduction

Dentistry and orthodontics are not an exception to the huge changes that technology is bringing about in this modern day in all fields. Laser technology has been introduced in both dentistry and medicine as a result of such technical improvement. "Light amplification by stimulated emission of radiation" is referred as Laser. It is a concentrated path of light energy, that moves around a single phase and all of its wavelengths travelling in the same direction. The effect of laser on the target tissues during a dental procedure will depend on the, exposure period.² Soft tissue lasers can be utilised to conduct surgical exposure of the tooth, frenectomy, and gingivectomy with greater accuracy, less pain, and less wound contraction. Enamel bonding and etching as well as bracket debonding are further laser applications. Lower level lasers may reduce discomfort and hasten tooth movement, among other effects. Before beginning a laser therapy, clinicians must be properly trained and informed of the safety concerns and risks related to lasers.²⁴

Basic Components of Laser

An optical resonant, which includes more than two mirrors, an active medium (such as a gas, dye, solid-state electrical device, or semiconductor), and an external energy source are the three main components of a laser device (pump source). The active particles in the active medium are typically excited by a flashlamp or electricity from external energy sources to

produce stimulated emission.

Following their release from the active medium, photons are subsequently amplified by mirrors in the optical resonant, where they eventually manifest as laser light.²⁴

Properties

i. Monochromatic

In contrast to traditional sources, which generate with a large wavelength, lasers emit light with a very small wavelength. Consequently, laser are of a single distinct color rather than having multiples.

ii. Collimation

While ordinary lights deviate in all directions, a laser beam has a fixed direction, size, and form.

iii. Coherent

In laser light, every light wave is the same.¹

1. Dental lasers

i. Argon lasers

Two wavelengths of light are produced by the argon laser, which uses this gas as its active medium.. Maximum absorption of the blue-green light at 514 nm occurs in tissues made up of pigmented substances like hemosiderin and melanin. Hard tissues and tissues without pigmentation have weak argon

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Quick Response Code

How to cite this article: Jakhar et al. - Innovations and Trends in Laser Applications for Orthodontics. HTAJOCD 2024

laser absorption at both wavelengths. This laser is frequently used in gingival surgery to prevent bleeding as well as for transillumination-based fracture and surface decay detection on teeth.³

ii. CO2 lasers

CO2 gas serves as the laser's active medium. In comparison to other dental laser systems, this wavelength has the maximum absorbance in hydroxyapatite and a very high absorption in water. The CO2 laser is frequently used for surgery of soft tissues due to its benefits, which include quick hemostasis and least depth of insertion. The tooth structure which surrounds surgical area needs to be preserved while employing a CO2 laser, though. Hard tissue applications are not appropriate for these lasers.⁴

Midline diastema occur due to hypertrophic labial frenum which is still implanted in the free gingival margin or on the palatine papillae. 25 The use of temporary anchorage devices, which are utilised to push the upper incisors through in the case of a gummy smile, can be complicated by this kind of low frenum. A short lingual frenum can result in ankyloglossia, which can create issues such as an abnormal swallow, uneven lower jaw growth, and a lower midline diastema. 26-27 For intraoral surgery involving significant amounts of soft tissue or dense fibrous tissues, a CO2 laser is the perfect tool. It is a preferred option for frenectomy due to the high rate of absorption by the 90% water-containing oral mucosal tissues. Both soft tissues and hard tissues respond favourably to this laser.²⁸

iii. Erbium lasers

These are currently the popular choice. Because these lasers can be used for both the soft tissues as well as hard tissue. Both wavelengths have the largest water and hydroxyapatite absorption of any dental laser. Erbium lasers work well to remove hard tissues because water and hydroxyapatite are abundant in both bone and teeth. For such uses, the soft tissues around can be removed with little heat impact on the pulp as the water in the tooth evaporates. However, because of their strong affinity for enamel and very weak coagulation ability, they are mostly employed for tooth preparation and caries removal rather than soft tissue surgery.⁵

iv. Nd:YAG laser

Its 1,064 nm wavelength absorbs more water and pigmented tissue than CO2 laser. The dense coagulation layer created by this causes long-lasting hemostasis. Because they are utilised in a direct contact mode, which offers the best control for cosmetic surgery, they are more appropriate for gingivoplasty. It has been used for removal of soft tissue in addition to surgical procedure. They could be used safely to do surgery close to the teeth because it only damages dental hard tissue. It demonstrates that the use of a diode laser can successfully and swiftly treat gingival overgrowth and inflammation. .6

v. Diode laser

In diode lasers semiconductor is used for the source of emission. Light in its range is greatly taken by tissues and penetrates deeply into soft areas, water and dental hard

tissues are little able to absorb it. For hemostasis, it is less effective than the argon laser. These could be used for soft-tissue surgery procedures.²

2. Uses of Lasers in Orthodontic Practise

It quickly established itself as a go to method for managing a range of orthodontic treatment related issues, from ceramic bracket debonding and enamel surface etching to mucogingival surgery. Different wavelengths of lasers can treat issues with both hard and soft tissues. Additionally, low intensity lasers were said to be helpful in reducing pain brought on by orthodontic arch wire placement.

i. Pain reduction

Patient experiences pain or discomfort for two to four days after delivering orthodontic appliances. A practical analgesic treatment for orthodontic patients is low-level laser therapy (LLLT), which has very low energy output and prevent to rise temperature above 36.5°C. CO2 laser has been proven useful while easing discomfort connected to the use of orthodontic force. The first archwire's application causes pain, which LLLT efficiently manages, but it has no effect on the beginning of discomfort after that point or on the day that is the most uncomfortable. As a new therapy option, induction of laser analgesia is simple in use, and does not have any adverse effects.⁷⁻¹⁴

ii. Tooth Movement

Accelerating tooth mobility and remodelling of the alveolar bone are both possible with low intensity laser therapy. They don't require any expensive or specialised technology, are simple to operate, and are non-invasive. Increases in the levels of fibronectin and type I collagen are brought about by the using low level laser therapy. On the traction side, while tooth movement it promotes the growth of connective tissue.

iii. Enamel Etching

Due to radiations, changes in enamel, such as recrystallization, lead to creation of many porosity and bubble-like structures. According to reports, laser etching in enamel and dentin results in a broken, unequal surface. A surface resistant to acids is produced by laser etching. Dental hard tissues exposed to laser radiation undergo changes in the calcium and phosphorus ratio, water and organic content, which results in production of durable, acid-resistant compound (slower the process of caries) YAG laser etching along with these two methods.¹⁵⁻¹⁷

iv. Enamel Reduction by Decalcification

Due to increased plaque buildup around the brackets after the bonding, enamel is highly susceptible for damage. For orthodontic patients, this frequently results in decalcification in enamel or the development of white lesions and is a serious issue. The enamel that has been laser-irradiated reportedly becomes acid resistant. By changing the crystalline structure of enamel, an argon laser can stop decalcification.¹⁸⁻²¹

v. Ceramic Bracket Bonding

The sticky resin can be weakened by applying laser irradiation, enabling light force being used while debonding. Both mono and polycrystalline ceramic brackets can be removed with a Nd:YAG laser when it is applied at 2 J

or higher, albeit the bond strength of the polycrystalline ceramic brackets is dramatically reduced more than that of the monocrystalline brackets. The labial surface of the bracket is heated by laser, where the energy is transferred via bracket into resin, caused softening of adhesive, which is the debonding mechanism.²²

vi. Light Curing by Lasers

To start polymerization, an argon laser is typically used combined with an initiator like camphoroquinone and a reducing agent like tertiary amine. With its peak activity centred at 480 nm, this photoinitiator system exhibits high sensitivity to light in the visible blue area. The monochromatic argon laser generates light under a range of wavelengths in the blue and green spectra, which makes it perfect for polymerizing composites. Argon lasers are utilised for adhering brackets with strengths that are on par with those obtained with traditional light-curing resins.¹

vii. Clinical Exposure of Impacted Tooth by Lasers

By exposing teeth in submucosal area to reveal the clinical part of crown for disimpaction of tooth and by conducting distal gingival excision in the area of the mandibular molars to allow eruption of second molars in the arch, a laser can manipulate soft tissue in variety of ways. It takes little time, and the result is a nearly bloodless field.¹

viii. Frenectomy

The insertion of upper labial frenum is commonly the cause of the diastema in upper central incisors. Lasers are used for deep frenulum resection and transeptal fibre incision to speed up the closing of space and prevent after treatment relapse.⁵ The laser enables faster healing without bleeding or the requirement for stitches. Within a few days, secondary intention healing takes place painlessly.²³

ix. Laser Holography

It is a brand-new instrument to calculate tooth movement. Accurate way for identifying movement is provided by laser holography. The study of movement and periodontal disease is significantly impacted by the pressures created inside periodontal ligament while the crown is loaded to various forces.¹

x. Bone Regeneration After Expansion

Orthodontic treatment frequently involves rapid maxillary growth 28-30. The mid-palatal suture's detachment from the center's larger bone mass can significantly alter the morphology of the maxillary arch. After expansion, three to four months retention period is often required for bone remodelling and regeneration. According to various studies, low-level lasers can hasten the widening of the mid-palatal suture and increase bone formation both during and after rapid maxillary development. It may aid in decreasing the retention period to prevent relapse.³¹

Soft Tissue Applications

In order to accurately and conveniently cut soft tissue, dentists use dental lasers. They provide bleeding control, produce little tissue damage, and may even lessen post-operative discomfort. Gingival recontouring, exposing immature teeth, frenectomies, and treating aphthous

lesions are examples of soft-tissue uses. They may be utilised to aesthetic gingival contouring inside the framework of a smile, maintaining tooth proportion before bracket insertion, lengthening a crown, treating an asymmetrical crown height, or shaping the gingival and interdental margins. The majority of soft-tissue uses for Nd:YAG lasers are frenectomies, papillectomies, and gingival incisions.³²⁻³³

Conclusion

It can be an extraordinary technique of treatment for many clinical disorders when applied skillfully and morally. Among the many benefits of laser therapy are enhanced dental hygiene and aesthetic results. A single laser that can handle all dental operations is still a long way off, despite the fact that lasers are one of the technological developments with undeniable potential. This is true for both hard and soft tissue laser procedures. An adjunctive therapy like lasers can significantly improve the overall operation in one's dental office, which is important to fulfill the commitment for offering the best dental care. More clinicians are starting to pay attention to laser today. However, a laser therapy strategy based on empirical research needs to be created. The benefits of lasers must be supported by more convincing research. Additionally, when using laser therapy, certain safety precautions must be followed and the potential risks of lasers must be considered.

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